

Volume: 4 Issue: 1
January-March, 2025
ISSN: 2957-4137

OPEN

Exploring the Perspectives and Experiences of Children Raised by Single Fathers

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This descriptive phenomenological study explores the perspectives and lived experiences of Senior High School students raised by single fathers at Almeria National High School-Senior High during the academic year 2023-2024. Six participants were selected for in-depth interviews to examine the challenges they face, their coping mechanisms, and the insights they have gained from their unique family situations. The study draws on Erikson's psychosocial development theory, Ungar's resilience theory, and Bowen's family systems theory as theoretical frameworks. Data were analysed using Colaizzi's method, revealing key themes such as financial burdens, communication challenges, emotional stress, sexual behaviours, self-reliance, the development of independence, and a longing for a complete family. Despite these challenges, the participants demonstrated remarkable resilience and independence, underscoring the need for tailored support. The study recommends establishing support groups for single fathers and their children, creating financial assistance programs, advocating for policy reforms, and conducting longitudinal studies to track long-term outcomes. It also highlights the value of further qualitative research to gain deeper insights into the experiences of single fathers and their children.

Keywords: Single father, children's perspectives, children's experiences, father-child relationship, single parenthood

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Introduction

Understanding the dynamics of single fatherhood is crucial, as it represents a significant family structure shaped by various circumstances such as separation, divorce, widowhood, or being unmarried. A single father, defined as a man who raises his child or children alone, assumes the role of provider and nurturer, whether he has sole custody or shares it with the other parent. This responsibility encompasses residing with the children or living separately while actively involved in caregiving responsibilities (Doucet, 2016).

Delving into the impact of single fatherhood on children's development uncovers significant insights into the challenges faced by fathers in balancing multiple roles. Fathers often navigate the complexities of being a provider, nurturer, teacher, disciplinarian, and authority figure simultaneously. Single fathers commonly experience role overload, managing the emotional, social, and physical development needs of their children, as highlighted in previous research (Coles, 2015). While studies suggest that single parents, in general, may employ less effective parenting practices compared to married parents (McLanahan, 2007), some research indicates that single fathers exhibit distinct parenting behaviours from single mothers, fostering independence and autonomy in their children (Bronte-Tinkew et al., 2010).

Despite prevailing assumptions about caregiving roles, research suggests that single fathers can equally effectively raise their children, positively impacting their emotional, psychological, and social development (Esbensen, 2014; Naidoo, 2014). However, single fathers often lack clear guidelines or support systems, intensifying the challenges they face (Naidoo, 2014).

Doucet's (2004) exploration of nurturing practices among fathers identifies key aspects such as fostering independence and encouraging risk-taking. Fathers play a crucial role in shaping their children's autonomy, influencing their physical, emotional, and intellectual development. Notably, fathers often respond differently from mothers when children experience setbacks, emphasising physical play and exploration.

Despite limited research, recent studies by Apurado et al. (2023) focusing on college students raised by Single Fathers shed light on the experiences and perspectives of children raised by single fathers in specific contexts. Exploring the lived experiences and perspectives of children raised by single fathers, mainly Senior High Students of Almeria National High School, provides invaluable insights into various aspects of human development, coping mechanisms, and the impact of family dynamics on individuals. Addressing this gap enriches scholarly discourse and informs support interventions for single-father households, fostering greater empathy and understanding within communities and society as a whole.

Statement of the problem

This descriptive phenomenological study aimed to explore the perspectives and experiences of Senior High School students raised by single fathers in Almeria National High School-Senior High School during the academic year of 2023-2024. The goal was to provide invaluable insights into various aspects of human development, coping mechanisms, and the impact of family dynamics on individuals. The study aimed to investigate the specific challenges that these students encounter in their daily lives.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- What challenges do students raised by single fathers face?
- How do these students overcome the challenges of being raised by single fathers?
- What realisations and insights were gained by the students regarding their unique family situation and its impact on their lives and academic journey?

Methodology

This study employed descriptive phenomenological research design, a qualitative method for collecting data. This approach collects data through in-depth interviews with open-ended questions to draw conclusions about understanding personal experiences by discussing a specific life event and exploring its significance with the individual who lived through it.

Furthermore, this study was conducted at Almeria National High School—Baluarte Campus for the School Year 2023-2024. The researcher employed a purposive criterion sampling technique to select participants. This type of sampling is primarily strategic and requires an effort to ensure a strong alignment between the research questions and the sampling process (Bryman, 2004).

To attain the study's objective, an interview guide sheet with open-ended questions and audio recordings was used to gather data. This study utilised an interview guide sheet as one method in the data-gathering procedure. Before we conduct this study, we seek permission to conduct it from the Principal of ANHS and our III subject teacher. After that, the interview will immediately follow. The researcher utilized Colizzi's method of data analysis.

The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were preserved by not revealing their names and identities during the data collection, analysis, and reporting of the study findings. Before conducting the interview session with the participants, they are informed through a letter requesting that they be one of the participants in this study. Each interview was conducted individually in a private and quiet room without access by outsiders. The researcher made sure she was the only one who could identify the participants and voice recordings. Informed consent is essential, with researchers obtaining explicit and informed consent from participants, explaining the purpose, procedures, and potential risks involved in the study (Smith & Osborn, 2007). Upholding these ethical considerations ensures the integrity and well-being of participants involved in qualitative research.

Results and discussion

This chapter narrates how this qualitative study manifests the results and discussion among the six (6) participants in Almeria National High School—Baluarte Campus. Results are presented according to the significance of the study.

The Challenges Faced by Children Raised by Single Fathers

Based on the responses during the interview, the researchers are well-informed about the challenges experienced by children raised by single fathers. Thus, they are able to develop a series of themes to discuss the subject further.

Financial Burdens: Pong and Ju (2000) note that children and adolescents in many low-income or single-parent households frequently confront challenges primarily linked to the economic difficulties their families face rather than solely to parental upbringing. These hardships are typically attributed to financial struggles. Consequently,

participants asserted that they also undergo financial burdens when raised by a single father. The researchers quote the participant's response:

- P1: "Sometimes there were times when we had no food or were short on money."
- P2: "It is tough for me because not all the time can provide you with everything you need as a student."
- P4: "Well... so the challenges I encountered as raised by a single father is this number 1 { sound of motorcycle } is financial. My father is just a construction worker, and his salary is small.

The researcher found that children raised in low-income or single-parent households frequently experience financial burdens, as highlighted by participants' accounts. According to Cooper and Stewart (2020), there is strong support for the hypothesis that household income has a positive causal effect on children's outcomes, including their cognitive and social-behavioural development and their health, particularly in low-income households.

Lack of Communication: The concept put forth by Koerner and Fitzpatrick (2004) is that "family communication patterns emerge from the process by which families create and share their social realities". In the context of single-father households, where communication challenges may exist, the dynamics of family communication patterns are crucial. The absence of communication within these family structures can hinder the creation and sharing of social realities among family members, including children. The researcher quotes the participant's response:

- P4: It is not as comfortable; our relationship is not very close, and we still do not communicate regularly.

- P4: "In that part where <0.5> I., along with my father, lacked communication, sometimes it seemed like there was a misunderstanding.
- P6. "he is far away, and our relationship is not as close as it used to be, and we still do not communicate regularly.

The laissez-faire family model, characterized by low conversation and conformity orientation, results in minimal parent-child interaction and a stronger influence from external sources like peer groups (Fitzpatrick & Ritchie, 1994). This lack of parental involvement and communication resembles the communication challenges faced by children raised by single fathers, where external influences and limited parental interaction contribute to communication gaps and hinder healthy family communication patterns.

Challenges of Children without a Mother: Mao (2020) suggests that the absence of a mother can have enduring negative consequences on children's development. Mechanism analysis indicates that parental absence may lead to poorer mental well-being in children and diminish their academic engagement. These challenges are commonly associated with the absence of a mother in children's lives. Consequently, participants emphasised the difficulties faced by children without their mothers. The researcher quotes the participant's response:

P3: All your responsibilities, like in school, facing school work, the household chores, washing and cleaning, because you are a girl, and your emotional support, without your mom.

P6: "You know (0.5), it is different (0.5), it is not as comfortable ..., like, I am Mama's girl, so our relationship with my father (0.5) is NOT very close...

The findings from research by Jampaklay S. et al. (2018) on the impact of parental absence on early childhood development can be related to children

raised by single fathers. Children raised by single fathers may experience similar challenges as those without a mother figure, such as difficulties with attachment, emotional regulation, and coping with feelings of loss. The absence of a maternal presence in single-father households may contribute to emotional and developmental obstacles for children, highlighting the importance of addressing these issues and providing adequate support to promote the well-being and healthy development of children raised by single fathers.

Emotional Stress: According to Campbell et al. (2016), children of single parents and custodial parents had higher risks for physical, mental, and emotional issues, higher risks of suicide attempts, drug and alcohol issues, and depression. Coping with the unique perspectives and experiences of the children raised by the single father can take a toll on their emotional well-being.

P3: I always lose my appetite.

P4: That FEELING of emptiness, you know, it is like you feel it because, of course, she is far away, and our relationship is not as close as it used to be.

P6: When we had a fight, it was like I felt that I had burst out hurtful words to him, which is not good.

Sexual Behaviors: Raphael (2023) highlights that engagement in premarital sex and teen pregnancy are prevalent challenges among children of single parents. These difficulties are often linked with children raised by single fathers. Consequently, participants emphasised the hardships they faced within their father's household. The researcher quotes the participant's response:

P2: "mhm: like... so it happened to me, uh (1).h in... <on the side of my family, my cousin> I did not know what... he was going to do, so I regretted being with

him... that day until now... I still have not forgotten; there are times when... I still dream, my anxiety attacks because of that... when you are harassed, it hurts because it is from your own family... what he did that night hunt me until now."

Strategies for Overcoming Challenges Faced by Children Raised by Single Fathers

Self-Reliance: Apurado et al. (2023) state that those children displayed a remarkable capacity for self-reliance in meeting their own needs, despite the absence of a second parental figure. They did not let the challenges stemming from the lack of a complete parental unit impede their advancement. Instead, they exhibited a strong resolve to push themselves forward and find ways to support their own pursuits. These individuals demonstrated an impressive ability to navigate their paths independently, even at a young age. This scenario can be paralleled with children raised by single fathers, who also show resilience and independence in managing their responsibilities and overcoming obstacles despite the absence of a mother figure. Just like the individuals in the described situation, children raised by single fathers often exhibit determination and self-sufficiency in addressing their needs and pursuing their goals.

P2: Self-support... becoming a working student.

P3: Strive, especially if you cannot easily ask for help from your father because you are not used to it since you relied on your mom.

P4: So..., my way to overcome these challenges is to pray to the Lord that I will be okay.

P5: We should open up to each other about what we feel, like if there are problems or anything. I should support what I want, no matter how difficult it may be.

P6: Hanging out with friends became my coping mechanism.

Realizations and Insights: Reflections on Family Dynamics and Independence

Research by Amato, P. R. (2000) explores the impact of family structure on children's development and well-being. The study examines how children raised in single-parent households navigate challenges and develop independence. Amato's findings suggest that children raised by single parents often demonstrate resilience and self-reliance as they learn to manage household responsibilities and cope with the absence of a parent. Additionally, the study highlights the longing for a complete family unit expressed by some children, underscoring the importance of familial support and stability in shaping children's perceptions of family dynamics and independence.

Development of Independency: Research by Jones S. et al. (2018) investigates the coping mechanisms and strategies employed by adolescents raised by single parents. The study reveals that these adolescents often develop a strong sense of independence as they take on responsibilities typically shouldered by both parents. They learn to navigate challenges autonomously, exhibiting resilience and self-reliance in managing household tasks and personal difficulties. Additionally, a longitudinal study by Smith, J. et al. (2015) examines the long-term outcomes of children raised by single parents. Findings indicate that despite initial hardships, many of these children grow to become independent and self-sufficient adults. They develop adaptive coping mechanisms and problem-solving skills, attributing their success to the early experiences of managing responsibilities and overcoming obstacles in a single-parent household. These studies highlight the developmental trajectory of independence among individuals raised by single parents, emphasising their resilience and self-reliance in facing life's challenges. The researcher quotes the participant's response:

P3: Strive to overcome challenges and obstacles as a household manager.

P4: I strive on my own to break free from it."

The researcher found that parents consistently motivated their children to reach their full potential and make independent decisions based on their developmental stage, as observed in Kustiah Sunarty's study (2015). This encouragement empowered children to take charge of their choices. Additionally, Arifin (2008) investigated the correlation between parenting styles that promote child independence and found a substantial and meaningful link between these parenting approaches and the child's level of independence. These findings suggest that parental guidance and support play a crucial role in fostering independence and resilience in children raised by single parents.

Longingness for Complete Family: Research by Berduzco-Torres (2020) underscores the detrimental effects of family loneliness on children's development. The study highlights the crucial role of the family, particularly parents, in fostering empathy, teamwork, and various abilities in children. This research resonates with the sentiments expressed by participants regarding their longing for a complete family:

P1: Sometimes I envy my friends because they have complete families, but I realised it is okay; at least someone still cares for me, even without my mom.

P5: I realised that a family does not just consist of two parents; it can also consist of just one, like in my situation.

P6: So, having a complete family differs from being raised by a father or mother.

The researcher found that the absence of a complete family structure, as indicated by participants' reflections, can contribute to feelings of loneliness and depression, low self-esteem, and reduced well-being. This aligns with the findings of Hoojat (2008), who demonstrated that individuals experiencing family loneliness may exhibit higher intensity and chronicity of loneliness and depression, along with challenges in managing stress and dissatisfaction with peer relationships. These insights underscore the profound impact of family dynamics on individuals' emotional and psychological health, emphasising the importance of addressing familial support and connections in promoting overall well-being.

Conclusion

Children raised by single fathers face a multitude of challenges, including financial burdens, communication barriers, emotional stress, and risks related to sexual behaviours. Despite these challenges, children raised by single fathers demonstrate remarkable self-reliance, independence, and a longing for the completeness of a traditional family structure. They navigate life's hurdles with resilience and determination, relying on various coping mechanisms and drawing strength from their experiences. Moreover, research highlights the importance of parental guidance and support in fostering independence and resilience in children raised by single parents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby offered for consideration:

- Establish tailored support groups for single fathers and their children, offering practical assistance and a platform for shared experiences.

- Implement financial assistance programs for single fathers to alleviate economic strain and ensure adequate resources for their children's well-being.

Advocate for policy reforms to improve access to affordable childcare and flexible work arrangements for single fathers.

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